

SOME INEQUALITIES OF GAUSS HYPERGEOMETRIC FUNCTION, ${}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2n}, b, \frac{1}{2n} + 1, -t^{2n}\right)$ FUNCTIONS

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ABSTRACT. This paper investigates some properties of Gauss hypergeometric function ${}_2F_1(a, b, c; -t^{2n})$ of specific parameters $a = 1/2n, b \geq 0, c = 1/2n + 1, n \in \mathbb{N}^+, b \in \mathbb{R}_+$. With these parameters, ${}_2F_1$ is monotonically decreasing as $|t|$ increases and is bounded within an interval $(0, 1]$. Furthermore, ${}_2F_1(1/2n, b_1, 1/2n + 1, -t^{2n}) > {}_2F_1(1/2n, b_2, 1/2n + 1, -t^{2n}), \forall 0 \leq b_1 < b_2, b_1, b_2 \in \mathbb{R}_+$. Additionally, we calculated the case where two functions with $n_1 < n_2 \in \mathbb{N}^+$ and the same b value related to their inequalities. The case yields a threshold point, $b_{th} = 1 + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2}\right)$, which makes ${}_2F_1(1/2n_1, b, 1/2n_1, -t^{n_1}) < {}_2F_1(1/2n_2, b, 1/2n_2 + 1, -t^{n_2}), b > b_{th}$. If $1/(2n_2) < b < b_{th}$, there is a $t_{th} > 0$ such that ${}_2F_1(1/2n_1, b, 1/2n_1, -t^{n_1}) > {}_2F_1(1/2n_2, b, 1/2n_2 + 1, -t^{n_2}), \forall t > t_{th}$.

Keywords: Inequality, Hypergeometric function, Inverse multi-quadratic

1. INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we explored the monotonicity and inequalities of Gauss hypergeometric function, specially, in the form ${}_2F_1(1/2n, b, 1/2n + 1; -t^{2n}), n \in \mathbb{N}_+, b \in \mathbb{R}_+$. This form arises in integration of inverse multiquadratics, $(1 + \|x\|^2)^{-b}$ [5], and expanded form, $(1 + (x - t)^{2n})^{-b}$. While ${}_2F_1(1/2n, b, 1/2n + 1; -t^{2n})$ form occurs in very simple case, their inequalities by the parameters n , and b are not covered by the known properties of the Gauss hypergeometric functions[4, 1, 3]. The primary goal of this paper is to provide the properties, focusing on inequalities relationships by the difference of n and b values, of the ${}_2F_1(1/2n, b, 1/2n + 1; -t^{2n})$ functions.

1.1. Definition and basic properties of Gauss hypergeometric function. In this paper, *GHF* was used as an abbreviation of Gauss hypergeometric function, and without special notation, upper case F denotes a next special form of GHF.

$$(1.1) \quad F(z, b, n) := {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2n}, b, \frac{1}{2n} + 1, -z^{2n}\right)$$

The superscript $+, -$ on some number set $\mathbb{X} = \mathbb{N}, \mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{R}$ indicate positive and negative elements of set respectively and zero is not contained without additional notation. For example, $\mathbb{X}^+ = \{x | x \in \mathbb{X}, x > 0\}$.

Definition 1.1 (Gauss hypergeometric function).

$$(1.2) \quad {}_2F_1(a, b, c; z) := \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_n (b)_n}{(c)_n} \frac{z^n}{n!}$$

where, $|z| < 1$, $c \notin \mathbb{N}^- \cup \{0\}$ and $(x)_n$ is a Pochhammer symbol which is defined as

$$(1.3) \quad (a)_n = \frac{\Gamma(a+n)}{\Gamma(a)}.$$

It is analytic everywhere on complex plane, \mathbb{C} , with principal branch $(1, \infty)$ [4]. With analytic continuation and Euler integral representation, next equation can be used for expanded complex version of the function if the integral is well defined[1].

For $\Re(c) > \Re(b) > 0$,

$$(1.4) \quad {}_2F_1(a, b, c; z) = \frac{\Gamma(c)}{\Gamma(b)\Gamma(c-b)} \int_0^1 \frac{t^{b-1}(1-t)^{c-b-1}}{(1-zt)^a} dt$$

where, $\Gamma(x)$ is a gamma function.

By the definition of GHF, GHF have next properties.

- Symmetric for a, b : ${}_2F_1(a, b, c; z) = {}_2F_1(b, a, c; z)$
- ${}_2F_1(a, b, c; z) = 1$ if $a = 0$ or $b = 0$ or $z = 0$.
- ${}_2F_1(a, b, b; z) = (1-z)^{-a}$

Pfaff's transform of GHF is a well-known linear transformation formula of GHF.

$$(1.5) \quad {}_2F_1(a, b, c; z) = (1-z)^{-a} {}_2F_1(a, c-b, c; \frac{z}{z-1})$$

and it is also valid for analytic continuation of GHF[2].

Derivative of GHF can be represented with contiguous relations of GHF[7]. One noteworthy example is a

$$(1.6) \quad z \frac{d}{dz} {}_2F_1(a, b, c; z) = a[{}_2F_1(a+1, b, c; z) - {}_2F_1(a, b, c; z)].$$

2. 2F1 FUNCTION OF SPECIAL FORM

2.1. Generating Integral. GHF, ${}_2F_1(a, b, c; z)$, of $a = 1/2n, b \geq 0, c = 1/2n + 1, z \leq 0$, is derived with scale value t from the next integral, for $z = -t^{2n}, t \geq 0$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$,

$$(2.1) \quad \int_0^t (1+x^{2n})^{-b} dx = t \cdot {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2n}, b, \frac{1}{2n} + 1, -t^{2n}\right)$$

Proof. Let, $x = ts$, then $dx = tds$,

$$(2.2) \quad \int_0^t (1+x^{2n})^{-b} dx = t \int_0^1 (1+t^{2n}s^{2n})^{-b} ds$$

and again substituting parameters, $s^{2n} = z, 2ns^{2n-1} ds = dz$,

$$(2.3) \quad ds = \frac{1}{2n} z^{1/2n-1} dz$$

Thus,

$$(2.4) \quad \int_0^t (1+x^{2n})^{-b} dx = t \frac{1}{2n} \int_0^1 \frac{z^{1/2n-1}}{(1-(-t^{2n})z)^b} dz$$

The right term of the above equation is an Euler integral representation of Gauss hypergeometric function Eq(1.4) with $a = 1/2n, c = 1/2n + 1$, even if $\Re(b) > \Re(\frac{1}{2n} + 1)$, since $a = \frac{1}{2n}$ is always smaller than c and $a \leftrightarrow b$ holds true.

$$(2.5) \quad {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2n}, b, \frac{1}{2n} + 1; z\right) = \frac{1}{2n} \int_0^1 \frac{t^{1/2n-1}}{(1-zt)^b} dt$$

□

This relationship also hold true for generalized hypergeometric function, ${}_pF_q, |z| < 1$ with series representation and $\alpha \neq 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} {}_pF_q\left(\begin{matrix} a_1, a_2, \dots, a_p \\ b_1, b_2, \dots, b_q \end{matrix}; z^\alpha\right) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a_1)_k (a_2)_k \dots (a_p)_k}{(b_1)_k (b_2)_k \dots (b_q)_k} \frac{z^{\alpha k}}{k!} \\ \int_0^z {}_pF_q\left(\begin{matrix} a_1, a_2, \dots, a_p \\ b_1, b_2, \dots, b_q \end{matrix}; t^\alpha\right) dt &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a_1)_k (a_2)_k \dots (a_p)_k}{(b_1)_k (b_2)_k \dots (b_q)_k} \frac{1}{\alpha k + 1} \frac{z^{\alpha k + 1}}{k!} \\ &\quad \because \frac{a}{a+k} = \frac{(a)_k}{(a+1)_k} \\ &= z \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a_1)_k (a_2)_k \dots (a_p)_k}{(b_1)_k (b_2)_k \dots (b_q)_k} \frac{(\frac{1}{\alpha})_k}{(\frac{1}{\alpha} + 1)_k} \frac{z^{\alpha k}}{k!} \\ &= z \cdot {}_{p+1}F_{q+1}\left(\begin{matrix} a_1, a_2, \dots, a_p, \frac{1}{\alpha} \\ b_1, b_2, \dots, b_q, \frac{1}{\alpha} + 1 \end{matrix}; z^\alpha\right) \end{aligned}$$

2.2. Properties.

Theorem 2.1 (Inequality 1). $\forall t$ and $b \in \mathbb{R}^+ \cup \{0\}, n \in \mathbb{N}^+, GHFs$ of form ${}_2F_1(1/2n, b, 1/2n + 1, -t^{2n}) = F(t, b, n)$ has next inequality for $0 \leq b_1 < b_2$,

$$F(t, b_1, n) \geq F(t, b_2, n)$$

and equality holds true when $t = 0$.

Proof. From Eq(2.1), because $(1+x^{2n}) > 0$,

$$(2.6) \quad (1+x^{2n})^{-b_1} \geq (1+x^{2n})^{-b_2}$$

is conserved through integration, thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^t (1+x^{2n})^{-b_1} dx &> \int_0^t (1+x^{2n})^{-b_2} dx \\ &\rightarrow tF(t, b_1, n) > tF(t, b_2, n). \end{aligned}$$

Without loss of generality we can assume $t > 0$, if $t < 0$, then $\int_0^t = -\int_0^{-t}$. Therefore, we get next

$$(2.7) \quad F(t, b_1, n) > F(t, b_2, n).$$

□

Theorem 2.2 (Monotonic property). $F(t, b, n)$ is a strictly monotonic decreasing function for $|t|$ value. That is, $\forall t > 0$

$$(2.8) \quad \frac{d}{dt}F(t, b, n) < 0$$

and the inequality is reversed for $t < 0$.

Proof. From Eq(1.6),

$$(2.9) \quad \frac{d}{dt}F(t, b, n) = \frac{1}{t}[(1 + t^{2n})^{-b} - {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2n}, b, \frac{1}{2n} + 1, -t^{2n}\right)]$$

Applying Pfaff's transform,

$$(2.10) \quad = \frac{1}{t(1 + t^{2n})^b} [1 - {}_2F_1\left(1, b, \frac{1}{2n} + 1, \frac{t^{2n}}{1 + t^{2n}}\right)]$$

Let $z(t) = t^{2n}/(1 + t^{2n})$, then $0 \leq z < 1$ and with Eq(1.4), the above GHF term can be represented as

$$(2.11) \quad {}_2F_1\left(1, b, \frac{1}{2n} + 1, z\right) = \frac{1}{2n} \int_0^1 \frac{(1-s)^{\frac{1}{2n}-1}}{(1-zs)^b} ds$$

, from the regions $0 < z < 1$ and $0 < s < 1$, the numerator and denominator of the RHS integral are always positive and $(1-zs)^{-b} > 1 \forall b > 0$. Therefore, $(1-s)^{\frac{1}{2n}-1}/(1-zs)^b > (1-s)^{\frac{1}{2n}-1}$ and consequently, we get

$$(2.12) \quad {}_2F_1\left(1, b, \frac{1}{2n} + 1, z\right) > \frac{1}{2n} \int_0^1 (1-s)^{\frac{1}{2n}-1} ds = 1.$$

Thus, for $t > 0$,

$$(2.13) \quad \frac{d}{dt}F(t, b, n) < 0$$

, and $F(t, b, n)$ is an even function, it is enough.

□

Theorem 2.3. $F(t, b, n)$ is bounded on $(0, 1]$, $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^+, b > 0$.

Proof. By the definition, Eq (1.2), $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} {}_2F_1(\dots, -t^{2n}) = {}_2F_1(\dots, 0) = 1$. It monotonically strictly decreases $\forall |t|$ by Theorem 2.2. Therefore, maximum value 1 exists at point $t = 0$, and with Eq (2.1), $F(t, b, n) > 0, \forall t \in \mathbb{R}$, it is bounded below by value 0. □

However, the function could not be treated as a probability function, since it is a non-integrable function.

Lemma 2.4. It is a non-integrable function, such that

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^s F(t, b, n) dt = \infty$$

Proof. With substitution integration, $t^{2n} = x$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^s F(t, b, n) dt \\ &= \int_0^{s^{2n}} \frac{1}{2n} x^{1/2n-1} {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2n}, b, \frac{1}{2n} + 1, -x\right) dx \end{aligned}$$

In $s^{2n} \rightarrow \infty$, Mellin transform of Gauss hypergeometric function permits us to determine the convergence, see 15.14.1 of [4]. Let $0 < \epsilon < \epsilon_0 = \min(\frac{1}{2n}, b)$, we have next

$$(2.14) \quad \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow \epsilon_0} \frac{1}{2n} \int_0^\infty x^{\epsilon-1} {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2n}, b, \frac{1}{2n} + 1, -x\right) dx = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow \epsilon_0} \frac{1}{2n} \frac{\Gamma(\epsilon)\Gamma(\frac{1}{2n} - \epsilon)\Gamma(b - \epsilon)}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2n})\Gamma(b)\Gamma(\frac{1}{2n} + 1 - \epsilon)}$$

The terms on the numerator, $\Gamma(\frac{1}{2n} - \epsilon)\Gamma(b - \epsilon)$ diverge to ∞ always as $\epsilon \rightarrow \epsilon_0$ for $b > \frac{1}{2n}$. If $b < \frac{1}{2n}$ then, next identity guarantees the same result.

$$(2.15) \quad \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow \epsilon_0} \int_1^\infty x^{\epsilon-1} {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2n}, b, \frac{1}{2n} + 1, -x\right) dx = \infty < \int_1^\infty x^{\frac{1}{2n}-1} {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2n}, b, \frac{1}{2n} + 1, -x\right) dx \quad \square$$

More precisely, the F converges to a reciprocal function, even though $b/2n > 1$.

Lemma 2.5. $\forall \alpha > 1$ and $b > \frac{1}{\alpha}$, $t \rightarrow \infty$

$$(2.16) \quad F(t, b, \frac{\alpha}{2}) \sim \Gamma(b)^{-1} \Gamma(\frac{1}{\alpha} + 1) \Gamma(b - \frac{1}{\alpha}) \frac{1}{t}$$

That is,

$$(2.17) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} t F(t, b, \frac{\alpha}{2}) = \Gamma(b)^{-1} \Gamma(\frac{1}{\alpha} + 1) \Gamma(b - \frac{1}{\alpha})$$

Proof. For $\alpha > 1$ and $b > \frac{1}{\alpha}$, Mellin transform of GHF is possible as

$$(2.18) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} t F(t, b, \frac{\alpha}{2}) = \int_0^\infty {}_2F_1(b, 1, 1, -x^\alpha) dx = \Gamma(b)^{-1} \Gamma(\frac{1}{\alpha} + 1) \Gamma(b - \frac{1}{\alpha})$$

Thus,

$$(2.19) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{F(t, b, \frac{\alpha}{2})}{\Gamma(b)^{-1} \Gamma(\frac{1}{\alpha} + 1) \Gamma(b - \frac{1}{\alpha}) \frac{1}{t}} = 1 \quad \square$$

Theorem 2.6 (Inequality 2). $\forall n_1 < n_2 \in \mathbb{N}^+$ and $b > 0$, there exists threshold value b_{th} such as

$$(2.20) \quad b_{th} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2} \right)$$

and

- (1) $b \geq b_{th}$: $\forall t, F(t, b, n_1) < F(t, b, n_2)$
- (2) $\frac{1}{2n_1} < b < b_{th}$: $\exists t_{th}$, s. t. $1 < t_{th}$ and $\forall t > t_{th}$, $F(t, b, n_1) > F(t, b, n_2)$

Proof. Define two function f, g for the given $n_1 < n_2$ and $b > 0$

$$(2.21) \quad f(t) := {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2n_2}, b, \frac{1}{2n_2} + 1, -t^{2n_2}\right) - {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2n_1}, b, \frac{1}{2n_1} + 1, -t^{2n_1}\right)$$

$$(2.22) \quad g(t) := (1 + t^{2n_2})^{-b} - (1 + t^{2n_1})^{-b}$$

The proof of (1) and (2) are enough to show that $f(t)$ has unique maximum point in $t < 1$ and only if $b < b_{th}$ there is unique negative minimum point at $1 < t$. The functions f , and g have next identities.

$$(2.23) \quad tf(t) = \int_0^t g(x)dx$$

$$(2.24) \quad t^2 f'(t) = \int_0^t xg'(x)dx = t(g(t) - f(t))$$

$$(2.25) \quad g(t) = f(t) + tf'(t)$$

From the definitions, $f(t) > 0$ and $g(t) \geq 0$ for $0 < t \leq 1$. We will first obtain positions of extreme values of g function and based on the properties, we will determine the properties of f function.

Lemma 2.7. $\forall b > 0, n_1 < n_2, g(t)$ has two extreme values at point $0 < t_0 < 1 < t_1$, and they are maximum and minimum points respectively for t_0 and t_1 .

Proof. Let a function $l(t)$,

$$(2.26) \quad l(t) = \left[n_2 \frac{t^{2n_2}}{(1 + t^{2n_2})^{b+1}} - n_1 \frac{t^{2n_1}}{(1 + t^{2n_1})^{b+1}} \right]$$

then, the function, $l(t)$ shares roots with $g'(t)$.

$$(2.27) \quad g'(t) = -\frac{2b}{t}l(t)$$

$l(t) = 0$ yields next equality.

$$(2.28) \quad \frac{1}{b+1} \ln\left(\frac{n_2}{n_1}\right) = \ln\left(\frac{1 + t^{2n_2}}{1 + t^{2n_1}}\right) - \frac{2(n_2 - n_1)}{b+1} \ln(t)$$

The RHS diverse to $+\infty$ as $t \rightarrow 0+$ and $t \rightarrow \infty$, and has unique minimum point, t_m . $t_m > 1$, if $b < 1$. Conversely, $t_m < 1$ if $b > 1$. In addition, $\ln(n_2/n_1)/(b+1)$ is positive for all $b > 0$ and $n_1 < n_2$. Therefore, in any case of b, n_1, n_2 , $g'(t)$ has two roots, t_0 , and t_1 , precisely, $0 < t_0 < 1 < t_1$. \square

Lemma 2.8. $f'(t)$ has an root at $t = t_{e_1}$, $t_0 < t_{e_1} < 1$ and if $b < b_{th} = 1 + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2}\right)$, there exists an unique root, t_{e_2} greater than t_1 .

Proof. For $0 < t < t_0$, $tg'(t) > 0 \rightarrow t_0^2 f'(t_0) > 0$. By the definition, $g(1) = 0 = f(1) + f'(1)$ and $f(1) > 0$. Therefore, $f'(1) = -f(1) < 0$. Since, $tg'(t) < 0$ at $t_0 < t < 1$, $t^2 f'(t)$ monotonically decreases in the region by Eq (2.24). Consequently, the root of $t^2 f'(t)$, $\exists! t_{e_1}, t_0 < t_{e_1} < 1$ by IVT.

For $t > 1$, a limit of $t^2 f'(t)$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$ is useful to determine the other roots.

$$(2.29) \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} t^2 f'(t) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} t(g(t) - f(t))$$

$$(2.30) \quad = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} t \left\{ \frac{1 - {}_2F_1(1, b, \frac{1}{2n_2} + 1, t^{2n_2}/(1 + t^{2n_2}))}{(1 + t^{2n_2})^b} \right.$$

$$(2.31) \quad \left. - \frac{1 - {}_2F_1(1, b, \frac{1}{2n_1} + 1, t^{2n_1}/(1 + t^{2n_1}))}{(1 + t^{2n_1})^b} \right\}$$

The asymptotic behavior of $(1 - {}_2F_1(1, b, \frac{1}{2n} + 1, t^{2n}/(1 + t^{2n}))) / (1 + t^{2n})^b$ at $t = \infty$ depends on the range of b . Using argument unity of hypergeometric function, see 15.4.ii of [4], next asymptotic equations are achieved by the cases.

- (1) $0 < b < \frac{1}{2n}$: $\frac{2nb}{2nb-1} t^{-2nb}$
- (2) $b = \frac{1}{2n}$: $t^{-1}[1 - \ln(t)]$
- (3) $\frac{1}{2n} < b$: $t^{-2nb} - t^{-1}\Gamma(b)^{-1}[\Gamma(\frac{1}{2n} + 1)\Gamma(b - \frac{1}{2n})]$

Therefore, the limit, Eq (2.30), have 5 cases of asymptotic equations of form,

$$(2.32) \quad p(t)t^{1-2n_2b} - q(t)t^{1-2n_1b} + c.$$

See Table 1.

TABLE 1. Asymptotic equation at $t = \infty$ [4]

b	$p(t)$	$q(t)$	c	Limit at $t = \infty$
$0 < b < \frac{1}{2n_2}$	$\frac{2n_2b}{2n_2b-1}$	$\frac{2n_1b}{2n_1b-1}$	0	∞
$b = \frac{1}{2n_2}$	$1 - \ln(t)$	$\frac{2n_1b}{2n_1b-1}$	0	∞
$\frac{1}{2n_2} < b < \frac{1}{2n_1}$	1	$\frac{2n_1b}{2n_1b-1}$	$-\Gamma(b)^{-1}[\Gamma(\frac{1}{2n_2} + 1)\Gamma(b - \frac{1}{2n_2})]$	∞
$b = \frac{1}{2n_1}$	1	$1 - \ln(t)$	$-\Gamma(b)^{-1}[\Gamma(\frac{1}{2n_2} + 1)\Gamma(b - \frac{1}{2n_2})]$	∞
$\frac{1}{2n_1} < b$	1	1	$\Gamma(b)^{-1}[\Gamma(\frac{1}{2n_1} + 1)\Gamma(b - \frac{1}{2n_1}) - \Gamma(\frac{1}{2n_2} + 1)\Gamma(b - \frac{1}{2n_2})]$	c

With the asymptotic equations in Table 1, we can vanish the $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} t^2 f'(t)$ when $b = b_{th} = 1 + \frac{1}{2}(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2})$, that is simply expressed with next cases.

$$(2.33) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} t^2 f'(t) = \begin{cases} \infty & b \leq \frac{1}{2n_1} \\ c > 0 & \frac{1}{2n_1} < b < b_{th} \\ 0 & b = b_{th} \\ c < 0 & b > b_{th} \end{cases}.$$

where c is an arbitrary constant comprise of Gamma function and b, n_1, n_2 values.

For $t > t_1$, $tg'(t) > 0$, then by the Eq (2.24), $t^2 f'(t)$ monotonically increases and its limit is shown in Eq (2.33). About $t^2 f'(t)$ at $t = t_1$,

$$(2.34) \quad \int_0^1 g'(t)dt = 0 > \int_0^1 tg'(t)dt, \because g'(t) \geq 0, t \in [0, 1]$$

$$(2.35) \quad \int_1^{t_1} tg'(t)dt < \int_1^{t_1} g'(t)dt < 0, \because g'(t) < 0, t \in (1, t_1]$$

Therefore, $\int_0^{t_1} tg'(t) dt = (t_1)^2 f'(t_1) < 0$. Finally, if $b < b_{th}$ there exists an another root, t_{e_2} where $t_1 < t_{e_2}$, of $t^2 f'(t)$ and it is unique for $1 < t$. As $f'(t)$ and $t^2 f'(t)$ are sharing non-zero roots and sign at each point, t_e , and t_{e_2} are roots of $f'(t)$ too. \square

Now, with the above results, $f(t)$ has a maximum point at $t = t_e$, $t_e < t_0 < 1$ and if $b < b_{th}$, there exists an unique minimum point $t_{e_2} > 1$. As, the limit of $f(t)$ for $\frac{1}{2n_1} < b$ is

$$(2.36) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} f(t) = \begin{cases} 0+ & b \geq b_{th} \\ 0- & b < b_{th} \end{cases}$$

We can conclude that the $f(t_{e_2}) < 0$ because, $f'(t) > 0 \forall t > t_{e_2}$ and $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} f(t) = 0-$. Finally applying intermediate value theorem to function f in the region, $t_{e_1} < t < t_{e_2}$, yields there exists an unique root $f(t) = 0$ in the region. \square

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

There are some special cases of $F(t, b, n)$ function[4]. In addition, $2n = 2^k$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_+$, cases were partially studied by some authors[6, 9].

TABLE 2. Special cases of $F(t, b, n)$

n	b	${}_2F_1(1/2n, b, 1/2n + 1; -t^{2n})$
1	1/2	$t^{-1} \ln(t + \sqrt{1 + t^2})$
1	1	$t^{-1} \arctan(t)$
-	$1/2n + 1$	$(1 + t^{2n})^{-1/2n}$

Fig 1 and 2 are plotting graphs of ${}_2F_1(1/2n, b, 1/2n + 1; -t^{2n})$ and special case of Table 2. Fig 3 is an example plot of Theorem 2.6 and its proof process. The implementation routine of GHF function was imported from *mpmath* library[8].

FIGURE 1. Plot graphs of $F(t, b, n)$ function for $b \geq 0$, $n = 1$. (a): From $t = -1$ to $t = 1$. (b): From $t = 0$ to $t = 100$. b values of each graph are noted in legend. The formulas after comma in the legend are the special cases of $F(t, b, n)$ corresponding to each b value.

FIGURE 2. Plot graphs of $F(t, b, n)$ functions. The left is from $t = 0$ to $t = 20$, and the right is from $t = 0$ to $t = 1$ for $b \geq 0$ and $n = 1, 2, 3, 8, 20$.

FIGURE 3. $n_1 = 2, n_2 = 5$ case plot. $b_{th} = 1.35$. (a): $f(t)$ graphs by b values in legends. (b): $tf(t)$ graphs and its converged values calculated with Eq (2.17), denoted as transparent dashed line. (c): $F(t, b, n)$ behavior by b values of each title for $n_1 < n_2$. The red line is n_1 and the blue line is n_2 graph.

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SOME INEQUALITIES OF GAUSS HYPERGEOMETRIC FUNCTION, ${}_2F_1(\frac{1}{2n}, b, \frac{1}{2n} + 1, -t^{2n})$ FUNCTIONS

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